

Phraseological Units Classification Expressed Through Colors in French Printed Media

Manzura Jamolovna Isroilova

Teacher, Termez State University

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 31 December 2022	In today's quickly evolving information era, interpreting data and comprehending the nuances of journalistic speech require the reader's undivided attention. Can comprehend irony, metonymy, and metaphor without understanding the journalist's original meaning. In this paper, a portion of the phraseological units employed to polish the journalist's text in the French mass media are examined.
Corresponding Author: Manzura Jamolovna Isroilova	
KEYWORDS: Press language, political text, journalist's speech, idiom, metaphor, metonymy, communicativeness.	

INTRODUCTION

Phraseology is a rapidly developing branch of linguistics, and researchers are still interested in studying the semantic and communicative properties of phraseological units and their functions. Because phraseological units are essential for textual information and expression, they have a special place in many texts.

The deliberate use of phraseological units allows not only to convey information comparable to the text in a concise manner but also to have a specific effect on the recipient's mind. The media actively supports this approach, and phraseological units in experienced journalists' statements become an effective linguistic persuasion tool.

Today, most people's perceptions of the world are formed through the lens of media coverage. Print media and the Internet are the most effective. The printed edition informs and interprets to readers about current events around the world. Based on this interpretation, a person's knowledge of the surrounding reality is formed. The journalist selects the language tools best suited to evaluating the event with the readers. Phraseological units are necessary expressive means of the newspaper text.

In today's society, mass media is pervasive in daily life and serves as the primary source of all information for many people. The mass media's ability to be informed quickly and continuously about critical national and international events is a significant advantage. The written press is a distinct genre characterized by the instantaneous reflection of every moment of reality. Newspapers have their style, in which the journalist's speech is very important in exchanging communicative ideas with the reader. Journalistic speech, a type of communication, has always

been important in shaping public opinion. This study examines text from France's most popular daily newspapers (Le Figaro, Le Monde, La Liberation).

MAIN PART

Textual enhancement relies heavily on phraseological units. They enhance the text by altering or accentuating the meaning of specific words. Phraseological turns are a particular stylistic device.

Utilizing phraseological units enhances the journalistic language and enables the reader to get information swiftly and concisely. They embellish the news and enhance its impact. Obviously, the student's social standing is significant.

Distinguishing characteristics of journalistic texts, in general, journalistic texts should be concise and engaging. The primary function of the media is to inform. Nonetheless, the written press also serves to "persuade" and "influence" public opinion [11]. Not all publications tackle the news in the same manner. Similar material may be handled differently by several newspapers. Some newspapers interpret facts by dramatizing them in order to shock or amuse the public, or to conform to their media orientation. In order to attain these objectives, the text is frequently reproduced using various kinds of speech to generate specific effects. Each newspaper has its own unique style. From a stylistic perspective, the lexicon of the written press is quite diverse.

Articles in the French press adhere to some journalistic ethics norms (we mean newspapers with a reputation in the country of their circulation: Le Monde, Le

Figaro, etc.), but the style is distinct from that of the yellow press.

Journalistic texts are distinguishable from other forms of texts by their use of phraseological phrases, especially the huge number of idiomatic idioms that occupy prominent positions in stable structures. Idiomatic idioms can also be used to describe a circumstance, concept, or occurrence. They are used to move the listener, make an impression, bring the ideas communicated to life, persuade, and draw attention. Phraseological phrases in the French printed press are linguistic units that indicate word clusters whose structure and meaning are frequently uncertain. Indeed, a linguistic community’s history and culture are reflected in its vocabulary. However, as Le Guerne points out, language is not “a direct observation of existing reality”: it “presupposes necessarily an intellectual interpretation”. In general, journalistic discourse:

- characterized by a high level of standardization;
- les pourparlers sont en cours entre, le rétablissement de la justice, l’occupation rampante;
- frequent use of the narrative infinitive (Et+sujet+verbe déclaratif à l’infinitif): *L’art de Lena Dunham tient à sa manière de laisser les personnages prendre chair, sans pour autant s’écarter du propos essentiel du récit.* [Le Monde, FRIDAY 29 JUILLET 2022];
- use of indirect speech; *De retour en France, elle l’admet: “Tout ça, c’était pour toi, Rosy”* [Le Monde, FRIDAY 29, JUILLET 2022];
- the presence of stylistic processes (metaphor, metonymy) and political-cultural reality: *Les Insoumis et les Verts se rejettent la faute. Le palais de l’Élysée; L’Assemblée nationale, La meilleure défense, c’est l’attaque; qui trop embrasse, mal étreint, Tel qui rit vendredi, dimanche pleurera, L’UE qui trop embrasse, mal étreint Euro: tel qui pleure dimanche mercredi rira, Qui vivra verra si les jours du régime syrien sont comptés* – journalists try to use the brightest tools, including phraseological units, to influence public opinion.

The analysis of political articles in French shows that expressions and idiomatic expressions are dominant in the written press. In order to limit the research, in this work we will pay attention to the active use of the following French phraseological units expressing color in written mass information: *balnc bec* – mother’s milk has not left her mouth (used in relation to older adults, in literal translation white muzzle), *aigle blanc* – gang leader (literally white eagle), *armes blanches* – cold weapon (literally white weapon), *billet blanc* – winning the lottery, *boule blanche* – getting a good grade on the exam, *canne blanche* – the blind, *respecter les cheveux blancs* – to show respect to the elderly, *fil de la poule blanche* – girls’ cosset, *sourire blanc* – to laugh unnaturally, *donner carte blanche à quelqu’un* – to give someone freedom, initiative, power, *faire travailler sa matière grise* – to perplex, *faire marron* – to cheat, to deceive, *voir la vie en rose* – to see the bright side of life,

voir rouge – eyes filled with blood, *donner le feu vert* – to give consent, *être blanc comme neige* – to be innocent, *broyer du noir* – to be depressed.

In French journalistic speech, idiomatic expressions expressed by the following colors are often used to give emotional expressiveness to journalistic speech and attract the reader:

– *de quoi donner une carte blanche à la Corée du Nord pour la poursuite de son développement nucléaire et de missiles.* (donner une carte blanche. def: Laisser l’initiative à quelqu’un, donner plein pouvoir – To give someone the full initiative); It is easier for a Francophone reader to understand the article well when knowing the meaning of this phrase. Its origin goes back to the 18th century. At the end of a military conflict, the victorious army would write down its terms on a blank piece of paper. The army that surrendered in the conflicts had only to obey! Even today, *carte blanche* (literally, a white card) symbolically gives absolute power to the person who receives it. The recipient of this *carte blanche* has the right to choose and decide what suits him [12]. So, *to continue the development of nuclear weapons and missiles, it is enough to give North Korea the entire initiative (permission) to realize all its wishes.*

– *la situation en Grèce est pourtant le fil rouge des enquêteurs de l’OLAF (Office européen de lutte antifraude).* (The situation in Greece is the main hot topic of those who participated in the European Anti-Fraud Office survey (literally red thread). [Le Monde, VENDREDI 29 JUILLET 2022]; *fil rouge-def*: “The red thread” is a metaphor for the “conducting thread” is the leading idea that ensures [13]. This phrase is believed to have been taken from Goethe’s text *Les affinités électives* published in 1809.

– *plages et cocotiers, paillotes sur pilotis, couleurs et douceurs des îles venant soudain nous servir sur un plateau une romance à l’eau de rose.* After the beaches and coconut palms, huts on the hills, and the colors and tranquility of the islands, we are suddenly greeted with a romantic hurler on the patmos. *Le Monde, WEDNESDAY 5 OCTOBER 2022; à l’eau de rose* – (literally in rose water) def. pleasant; soft; drunk; very easy; playing on simple emotions; For the first time in the 15th and 16th centuries, rose water, called “rose water”, was obtained by distilling rose petals, a distillation process that Alain Ray later suggests that the use of this expression for women may have appeared in the late 19th century, but at the beginning of that century (for example, in 1826 or 1833) there are several works that are used; and Claude Dunéton even finds it in Dumoncel’s *L’intérieur des comités révolutionnaires*, written at the end of the 18th century [12].

– *le groupe (TotalEnergies) veut accélérer dans le gaz et les renouvelables, mais il cherche et trouve encore de l’or noir.* The group wants to accelerate in gas and renewables, but it is still looking for and finding black gold. [Le Figaro, mercredi 5 octobre 2022]; *l’or noir* (literally

black gold). Oil and the wealth that comes with it. The expression appeared with the discovery of oil. It is derived from yellow gold, a metallic symbol of wealth, and represents oil as a precious resource. Black, of course, refers to the color of oil.

– ...*bien sûr, l’université propose des aménagements, mais cela implétes souvent de rater des cours, qu’il faut ensuite rattraper au prix de nuits blanches. [Le Monde, SAMEDI 22 septembre, 2022] ...of course, the university offers accommodation, but this often means that you have to make up for missed classes at the expense of sleepless nights. nuits blanches* (literally, white nights) is a sleepless night in a negative sense. Such phraseological units are often found in journalistic speech.

Phraseological units are in a perpetual state of flux and obsolescence. As a result of its occasional use in conversation, it progressively enters the archaic lexical layer. With the passage of time, phraseological units are updated in the author’s speech in line with the context of this archaic meaning, enriching the language’s vocabulary, which is a fundamental component of any language. It is difficult to count the number of idiomatic expressions in a language with precision. Mastering phraseology is a crucial component of journalistic ability, as journalistic texts are replete with phraseological units (different, of course, from fiction). At the semantic level, phraseological units are incredibly diverse, and idiomatic expressions strengthen the emotional expressiveness of speech, which in turn serves to captivate the reader.

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